

DATA MANAGEMENT MANUAL FOR CLINICAL TRIALS UNITS NEW STARTERS

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AUTHORS and CONTRIBUTIONS

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Related Infographics

- What is Data Management Infographic Flyer v1.0
- Introduction to Data Management Infographic Flyer v1.0
- Data Management Through the Lifecycle of a Trial Diagram v1.0

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ABBREVIATIONS / GLOSSARY

Abbreviation	Meaning
AE	Adverse Events
ACDM	Association of Clinical Data Management
CI	Chief Investigator
CRF	Case Report Form
CSV	Comma Separated Variable
CTIMP	Clinical Trial of an Investigational Medicinal Product
DM	Data Manager
DMP	Data Management Plan
eCRF	Electronic Case Report Form
EDC	Electronic Data Capture
GCP	Good Clinical Practice
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTA	Human Tissue Authority
IMP	Investigational Medicinal Product
MHRA	Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency
MP	Monitoring Plan
pCRF	Paper Case Report Form
QA	Quality Assurance
QC	Quality Control
QoL	Quality of Life
RA	Risk Assessment
SAE	Serious Adverse Events
SDV	Source Data Verification
SWAT	Study With a Trial
TMF	Trial Master File
TMG	Trial Management Group
TSC	Trial Steering Group
UAT	User Acceptance Testing

1. INTRODUCTION TO CLINICAL TRIALS AND OTHER WELL-DESIGNED STUDIES

A clinical trial is a research project that compares two or more treatments in patients with a particular condition or at risk of a condition to help generate high quality evidence about which is the more effective treatment or preventative strategy. The treatment being investigated in a clinical trial can be a medicinal product, a procedure, a device or another type of therapeutic intervention. Clinical trials are an essential part of the process of evidenced based practice and can help guide treatment decisions for both health care professionals and patients. Clinical trials are an important part of the pathway by which new medicinal products and devices can obtain a licence.

Well-designed studies are research that do not fall under the category of clinical trials, such as observational studies.

Clinical Trials of an Investigational Medicinal Product (CTIMPs) and some clinical device trials can be designed in a number of ways to prevent bias in research results:

- Blind - where the participant does not know which arm (group of participants receiving a specific treatment (or no treatment) of the study they are in
- Double blind, where neither the participant or the treatment team know which arm of the study the participant is in,
- Open, where the participant and the treatment team know the arm.

All clinical trials with more than one arm can be randomised where a participant is assigned to a particular arm at random, most frequently by an algorithm embedded within the trial database.

Many clinical trials start as a small-scale pilot or feasibility study, before using a refined methodology for a full-scale trial.

CTIMPs generally fall into 4 phases, although some trials will have a pre-clinical phase and a phase 0 in which very small numbers of participants are given the trial medication.

- Phase I trials are small scale trials in healthy participants to test for drug safety and efficacy. These are closely monitored trials and will often be carried out in specialist residential trials units. In cancer studies, phase I trials are usually on participants who have the cancer being targeted by the IMP.
- Phase II trials are medium scale trials testing the IMP on the target population to determine efficacy and side effects. These trials may titrate dose to find the optimal dose of the IMP for different age groups, dose/kg body weight, etc.
- Phase III trials test the IMP on a large number, possibly thousands, depending on the condition that the IMP is treating, of the target population. A phase III trial determines therapeutic effect and will often compare the drug to existing treatments and/or placebo.
- Phase IV trials are post-marketing surveillance after a drug has been licenced. These trials aim to collect more data on the drug and its side effects, long term risk/benefit analysis and efficacy in a wider population.

2. INTRODUCTION TO DATA MANAGEMENT, THE ROLE OF A DATA MANAGER AND THE DATA LIFECYCLE OF A TRIAL

Data management refers to the processes involved in planning, collecting, organising, processing, storing and maintaining data within research trials for the duration of the study. Good data management practices and processes are essential when conducting research to ensure high quality research output and data integrity i.e. ensuring that data is accurate, consistent and complete. This includes effectively managing the data itself, along with associated data systems/databases and relevant data-related study documentation.

Data management begins at study set-up where data management planning takes place, through the live study period involving the day-to-day management of data and its collection, to closure and beyond where data is analysed, preserved and shared for use and publication.

Research data management can be seen in terms of a data lifecycle, which illustrates the data flow throughout the study. Each stage of the study requires different data-related activities, and the role of a Data Manager is to ensure that these activities and the relevant processes are in place, allowing the research data to be managed effectively:

STUDY SET-UP

Planning: Planning takes place during the trial set-up stage to develop and plan data management for the opening of the study. Data management tasks at this stage include:

- Writing the data management plan
- Collaborating with key contacts such as the Chief Investigator, Trial Manager, Trial Statistician and Information System Developer to develop the system specification and data capture requirements (including any reports and study management that will be required)

- Developing the metadata (a document containing all variables and validations used to collect the data and inform the database build) and Case Report Forms (CRFs)
- Developing testing scripts and testing the database
- Providing input into the protocol (data management section)
- Developing training documentation and videos
- Obtaining all required sign offs for data management documentation

OPEN TO RECRUITMENT

Data Collection, Data Processing: After the study opens to recruitment, data collection takes place and the data is processed and cleaned by the Data Manager to ensure that it is complete, accurate and able to be used. Tasks here include:

- Data querying
- Processing change requests/form amendments/new forms and testing
- Producing TMG, TSC and internal project team reports (e.g. recruitment, withdrawals, follow up)
- Data cleaning
- Carrying out quality control checks of data
- Carrying out audit trail checks
- Data monitoring (toxicities, follow ups, withdrawals)
- Completing central monitoring and any site monitoring as required
- Ensuring essential study documents are up to date and regularly reviewed
- Answering day to day site queries

STUDY CLOSURE

Analysis, Preservation, Sharing, Re-use: At the end of the study, the data is prepared for analysis and the research written up for publication. Data is required to be preserved via archiving for future use and to validate the research findings. Where required, data should be shared and be accessible for future research. Data management actions for closure include:

- Ensuring all data queries are closed
- Working closely with sites and the Trial Statistician to clean data and prepare a final data export
- Locking the study database
- Working with Trial Manager to assist in trial close out tasks, including ensuring sites are closed appropriately
- Contributing to the final report to funders and papers assigned on the publication policy

3. DATA MANAGEMENT REGULATIONS (GCP MHRA HTA GDPR)

A crucial element of managing research data is adhering to the relevant trial governance and data management regulations to ensure that all data is being managed legally and compliantly.

Good Clinical Practice (GCP)

Good Clinical Practice (GCP) is a set of internationally recognised ethical and scientific quality standards for conducting clinical research that involves the participation of human subjects. Compliance with GCP principles ensures that the rights, safety and wellbeing of research participants are protected and that research data is credible, of high quality and that data integrity is protected.

GCP training and compliance is a legal requirement for individuals working on clinical trials of investigational medicinal products (CTIMPs), but GCP training is recommended as best practice for all staff involved in research, including non-CTIMPs. Training must be retaken every two years.

Good data management processes are required to be in place within a research trial to ensure GCP principles are being followed.

Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA)

The Medicines and Healthcare Products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) is a UK government agency responsible for regulating medicines and medical devices to ensure their safety. The MHRA is involved in regulating clinical trials, providing regulatory guidance and monitoring compliance for medicines and medical devices to ensure participant safety within a clinical trial.

The MHRA are required to carry out inspections within organizations conducting CTIMPS, either routinely or triggered by suspected or reported violations, to assess compliance with clinical trial regulations. Ongoing MHRA approval and strict safety reporting is required in order to conduct research within CTIMPs, and the MHRA may prevent a clinical trial from continuing if its processes are not compliant.

Within data management, MHRA regulations relate to GCP adherence, management of safety data (e.g. all potential Serious Adverse Events (SAEs) are adequately monitored in the trial database to ensure timely reporting), and ensuring that the necessary data management processes are in place to maintain data integrity, so that data is complete, consistent, accurate and reliable. Examples of this include maintaining a clear audit trail for data collected in the data system and ensuring that no unauthorised changes are made to data (e.g. by managing database access).

Human Tissue Authority (HTA)

The Human Tissue Authority (HTA) is the independent regulator of organisations that remove, store and use human tissue for research. They inspect organisations and provide guidelines to ensure that human tissue is being collected and used within research trials safely and ethically, and with full consent.

Data management tasks to comply with this relate to sample management, ensuring that consent is adequately captured from participants for the collection and use of their samples within a trial, dates of consent are captured and that where participants have withdrawn consent for use of samples, the required actions are implemented (e.g. the relevant organisations are contacted to ensure previously provided samples are destroyed).

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is a legal framework for ensuring that personal data is processed lawfully and safely by requiring robust processes for handling and storing this information. Personal data relates to any information whereby the research participants can be identified directly or indirectly. GDPR specifies that all personal data must:

1. Be processed lawfully, fairly and transparently
2. Be kept to the original purpose
3. Be minimised (i.e. Only the personal data that is necessary is collected)
4. Have the accuracy upheld
5. Be removed if they are not necessary
6. Be kept confidential and their integrity maintained

Each of these principles need to be adhered to when managing or sharing personal data within a research study. Where personal data is collected, the justification for collecting this should be detailed within the Data Management Plan and unnecessary data should not be collected from participants. Adequate procedures and documentation also need to be in place for data removal if a study participant withdraws consent for their data to be used within the study.

4. KEY PRINCIPLES AND CONSIDERATIONS FOR A DATA MANAGER IN THE SET UP OF A CLINICAL TRIAL:

A) CASE REPORT DESIGN

A case report form (CRF) is used to collect data in a trial. CRF design can involve trial managers, statisticians, the co-investigators and data managers. The design of the CRF will ensure only data set out in the protocol for planned analyses is collected and that all regulatory requirements are met.

CRFs can be paper (pCRFs) or electronic (eCRFs). Data on pCRFs need to be entered into the database, whereas the data on eCRFs are entered directly into the database. The use of pCRFs makes data entry more time consuming and there is a greater chance of data entry errors. ECRFs can also contain validation and edit checks in real time to query the data upon entry.

Important things to note when designing CRFs:

- Include a participant identification number and date the form was completed on all forms
- Ensure there are CRF completion guidelines to accompany trial specific CRFs with details on good documentation practice, such as 'if an incorrect entry is made, cross it out with a single line (do not obscure the original entry). Initial and date the entry and then enter the correct data'
- Do not collect the full date of birth as standard. Consider either collecting the Month/Year or Year only. If age is an inclusion criterion, collect age instead.
- Only collect data related to the protocol.
- Collect the raw data measurements rather than implied result (with the exception of age as explained above).
- Use coded entries and drop down code list entries.
- Consider the format type of each data variable and associated unit.
- Minimise the use of text fields.
- Avoid using abbreviations that are ambiguous or could be interpreted differently.
- When completing the pCRF/eCRF, avoid using abbreviations in text fields (other than NA - Not Applicable, ND - Not Done, NK - Not Known and UNK - Unknown) and acronyms, unless they are approved medical abbreviations known to be acceptable.
- Specify decimal points and number of places required where actual values are required for certain data points.
- Unit measurements should always be specified.

B) DATA MATRIX AND DATA DICTIONARY DESIGN

A data matrix is a spreadsheet used to capture all of the fields that will make up all of the CRFs used for a particular study. As well as the fields, it will capture the CRF name, the variable name, the response options (if required) branching logic (if required) any necessary validation.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
3											
4											
5											
6	CRF		Variable / Field				Text	Text	Text		
7	Name	Section Header	Name	Field Type	Field Label	Response options	Validation	Validation	Validation	Identifier?	Branch Logic Expression
8							Type	Min	Max		
9											
10											
11											
12											
13											
14											
15											
16											

Figure 1: Example of data matrix headings.

- Creating a data matrix helps to pre-define the variable names and branching logic ahead of the database build
- The data matrix can be used for testing – individual fields can have a pass/fail status and/or the matrix can be compared with the data dictionary output from the database to ensure they match
- It is important to get study statistician sign off when using a data matrix for a database build
- It is important to bear in mind the variable name length – for example, in STATA, there is a maximum character length of 32 characters
- A new version of the data matrix should be created if there is a change request/change to the database during the trial so that they match
- A data matrix is good for auditing purposes

C) DATABASE SPECIFICATION

A database specification document should be written prior to the build of a database, to ensure that the requirements of the study and communication process between the study team and database developer are clearly documented and understood by both parties. The document should record the agreement of requirements and timescales for completion and will show how a build evolves from concept to completion.

The database specification document should record and reference the location of all build requirements, such as:

- Metadata / Data Matrix

- CRFs
- How Data Should flow
- Validations
- What data should be entered to the database
- What reporting is required

Each database specification will be unique to the trial or study.

D) User Acceptance Testing

Data Management plays a pivotal role in ensuring that data collected during clinical trials are accurate, reliable, and compliant with GCP. User Acceptance Testing is a key phase in this process, as it involves testing systems, processes, and data to verify that they meet GCP requirements.

Key Considerations for UAT

1. Protocol Compliance

- **Protocol Alignment:** Ensure that the UAT process aligns with the study protocol, including data collection, processing, and reporting requirements specified in the protocol.

2. Data Validation

- **Data Accuracy:** Verify that the data collected and processed during UAT accurately reflects the source data from clinical trials.
- **Data Integrity:** Assess the integrity of the data to ensure that it has not been altered or tampered with during the data management process.

3. System Validation

- **eCRF Systems:** Ensure that Electronic Case Report Form (eCRF) systems used for data collection and management are validated according to GCP requirements.
- **Database Validation:** Validate the integrity of the database structure, data dictionaries, and data validation checks.

4. User Training and Documentation

- **Training:** Provide adequate training to users participating in UAT, emphasising the importance of GCP compliance.
- **Documentation:** Maintain clear and comprehensive documentation of UAT processes, including test plans, test scripts, and validation reports.

5. Traceability

- **Data Traceability:** Establish clear traceability of data from source to destination, ensuring that all data manipulation is well-documented and can be audited as per GCP requirements.

UAT Testing Scenarios

When conducting UAT in compliance with GCP, consider the following testing scenarios:

1. Data Entry and Validation

- Verify that data entry screens align with the study protocol.
- Confirm that data validation rules and checks are correctly implemented.
- Ensure that data entered in the system is consistent with source documents.
- Ensure that user access roles are correctly tested to ensure access to correct forms / functions on the database.

2. Data Export and Reporting

- Test data export functionality to generate reports as per the study requirements.
- Validate that data exports do not compromise the privacy and confidentiality of study participants.

3. Audit Trail and Logging

- Confirm that the system generates comprehensive audit trails for data changes and user actions.
- Ensure that the audit trail is maintained securely and complies with GCP's data integrity standards.

4. System Performance

- Test system performance under various loads to ensure that it can handle the expected volume of data and users during the clinical trial.

Documentation and Reporting

Maintain detailed documentation of UAT activities, including test plans, test results, deviations, and corrective actions taken. UAT reports should clearly demonstrate compliance with GCP standards and ensure transparency and accountability in the data management process.

E) TRAINING DATABASE USERS

GCP guidelines emphasise the responsibility of sponsors and investigators to ensure that all personnel involved in the conduct of a clinical trial are qualified and adequately trained. This includes training in the use of databases if they are part of the trial's data management process.

Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs): Develop and implement SOPs that outline the specific procedures for database use in the context of the clinical trial. These SOPs should cover data entry, data verification, data validation, and data security protocols.

Role-Specific Training: Tailor training programs to the roles and responsibilities of staff members. Those responsible for data entry and management should receive training specific to database use, while others may require broader training on clinical trial conduct.

Data Integrity and Security: Emphasise the importance of data integrity and security during training. Ensure that staff understand how to maintain the confidentiality and integrity of trial data, including proper handling of electronic records.

GCP and Regulatory Requirements: Ensure that staff are familiar with GCP guidelines and any relevant regulatory requirements related to data management. Training should emphasise compliance with these standards.

Hands-On Training: Provide practical, hands-on training that allows staff to become proficient in using the specific database software or tools employed in the trial. This may include training sessions, workshops, or online modules.

Continuing Education: Encourage ongoing learning and professional development. Clinical trial staff should stay up-to-date with changes in database technology and best practices in data management.

Documentation: Maintain records of staff training, including dates, content covered, and individuals trained. This documentation can be important for regulatory inspections and audits.

Quality Control and Monitoring: Implement a system for quality control and ongoing monitoring of database use. Regularly assess data accuracy and completeness, and provide feedback and additional training as needed.

Communication: Foster open communication among staff members and encourage them to report any issues or concerns related to database use promptly.

A user manual for database aimed at site staff should include information on database structure, user roles and data entry procedures. It should guide site staff on data integrity, patient privacy, and regulatory compliance, and offer troubleshooting guidance for common issues. Regular updates are crucial to maintaining relevance as the database or trial requirements evolve.

F) DEVELOPING A DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)

Developing a DMP is essential practice to ensure that the data collection adheres to regulatory requirements. The DMP is a document that outlines all the details and information about the processes that will be involved in managing the trial from beginning to end. It is vital that the DMP should be completed and reviewed before starting a trial requirement. DMP is a dynamic document that should be amended to add/modify processes at any stage while delivering the trial.

Important points to note when developing a DMP.

- Include a concise summary of the study objectives and the methodology for administering the treatment. This includes the anticipated schedules for commencing recruitment,

implementing the intervention, conducting follow-ups, and concluding the trial in preparation for data analysis.

- Define the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the study.
- Identify the screening process and participant consent.
- List the events schedule and define all the forms that will be used on each event.
- Include details regarding randomization prerequisites including; considerations for blinding and unblinding in both database management and access, whether the randomization process will be automated through the Electronic Data Capture (EDC) system or conducted manually, Implementing randomization checks is advisable to ensure participants are randomized as intended.
- Outline the roles and responsibilities, clearly defining which individuals will undertake specific tasks and the methods they will employ to carry them out.
- Establish a defined procedure for addressing missing data. Employing standardized missing data codes is a recommended practice, as it facilitates an end-of-study review to identify the causes of missing data and informs strategies to prevent them in future studies.
- Define the communication between trial individuals in cases like reporting AEs and SAES.
- Define the database access request procedure.
- Identify reporting requirements and ensure that the database will provide all the required reports.
- List all the training documents that have been developed to train users of the EDC system, and relevant work instructions.
- Include plans for deviations and how these will be actioned and recorded.
- Include details of trial specific EDC requirements that been implemented,, for example, if the system will send automatic notifications, and how these function.
- Data monitoring plan could be separate document or could be included within the DMP.
- Define data cleaning procedures including individuals' responsibilities.
- Define any Automatic/Manual edit checks.
- Define procedures for study close out and data lock.

5. KEY PRINCIPLES AND CONSIDERATIONS FOR A DATA MANAGER IN A CLINICAL TRIAL THAT IS OPEN TO RECRUITMENT:

A) MAKING CHANGES TO DATABASES WHEN A TRIAL IS OPEN

During recruitment, the Data Manager provides support for Database related queries, a ticketing system should be used to enable the trial team to report changes/issues. If any queries include major changes in the components of the Database or Workflow of the developed trial, then the possible risks and impact on data collected should be fully assessed and documented and agreed with the Trial Manager and Chief Investigator prior to any development work.

After a major change request is agreed the Functional Specification document should be updated. The changes should be developed in a test system and fully tested following the principles of User Acceptance Testing above. Following successful testing and approval changes can be released to the live system. The Trial Manager should be informed and in turn inform sites.

B) WRITING DATA QUERIES

The UK Clinical Trial Regulations and Good Clinical Practice guidelines specify that the study sponsor must ensure clinical trial data is accurately reported, recorded and verified to ensure patient safety and scientific integrity.

A data query is used to clarify or resolve any discrepancies or inconsistencies found in a data set to ensure high quality, reliable and accurate data.

Data queries are generated during validation checks and data cleaning processes. Data queries are typically generated by the data manager of the trial or study, which are then received by the site that is responsible for either clarifying a response or correcting an error. Once the site has responded to the data query and completed any subsequent actions, the data manager reviews the response and determines whether the query has been adequately answered. If the data query has been answered adequately, the data manager can close the data query. However, if the data query response has not been answered adequately or the answer is ambiguous, the data manager must re-raise the data query with the site for further clarification.

CRFs/eCRFs should be designed to effectively minimise data queries and databases should include validations that automatically pick up inconsistencies in the data, such as an unlikely date of birth etc., and flag the discrepancies to the attention of the site staff entering the data for a manual recheck. However, due to human error and technological inaccuracy, the need for verification of data may still be required.

The most important characteristic of a data query is clarity. The recipient of the data query should be easily able to understand what clarification is needed and why. An ideal data query should:

- Identify the issue
- Explain why it is an issue
- Explain what action is required from the site to address the query

Examples of good data queries:

- The screening APTT ratio is missing; however, this is a protocol required assessment. Please could you confirm the screening APTT ratio result and update the missing field?
- The participants month and year of birth has been recorded as 12/1994, however, this does not match the participants month and year of birth at enrolment (01/1963). Please could you check and confirm the correct month and year of birth of the participant, and then update where required?
- The participants blood pressure has been recorded as 999/900, however this is not compatible with life. Please could you check and confirm the blood pressure value?

Things to avoid:

- Leading queries.
- Double negatives.
- Too much text.

C) DEVELOPING REPORTS FOR INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL COMMITTEES

A range of internal and external reports are routinely required which require data management input. These can include:

1. **Project team reports** - updates on recruitment, data collection, CRF completion, protocol non-compliances
2. **TMG reports** – updates on recruitment, screening, participant withdrawals, participant death, follow up, CRF completion, protocol non-compliances, SAEs
3. **TSC reports** – recruitment, withdrawals, SAEs, primary outcome data
4. **Site reports** – outstanding data queries, outstanding/missing CRFs

It is useful to discuss with the relevant teams/groups/committees what data will be routinely required for each individual study and if any additional reporting is required ahead of meetings. Data can be extracted from the study database or relevant spreadsheets to populate the required information for the reports. The trial statistician can assist with data extraction where necessary or if complex extraction code is required.

D) MONITORING (Central and On-Site)

Monitoring is defined as ‘the act of overseeing the progress of a clinical trial, and of ensuring that it is conducted, recorded and reported in accordance with the protocol, Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), Good Clinical Practice (GCP) and the applicable regulatory requirements. GCP also states that if monitoring identifies serious and/or persistent non-compliance on the part of a site, then the sponsor should terminate the sites participation in the trial and the regulatory authorities should be notified.

It is therefore essential that all trials and studies have include documents that detail potential risks to participants and data, and determine how they will be mitigated by monitoring procedures.

There are two types of monitoring; Central and On-site.

Central Monitoring

Central monitoring activities should be carried out in accordance with the monitoring plan (MP). It involves the review of trial data from CRFs, operational activity and other data provided by the site to produce metrics and queries, at a location remote from the site. Analysis of the metrics obtained from central monitoring can then be evaluated and used as indicators to adapt the trial monitoring procedure or trigger escalation procedures.

General central monitoring activities should be reported according to the MP, and by tabling the generated report at a TMG meeting.. Examples of general central monitoring activities include:

- Recruitment figures per site/ overall
- Non-compliances per site/ overall
- Withdrawals per site/ overall
- Data completeness per site/ overall
- Data queries per site/ overall

On-Site Monitoring

On site monitoring involves the review of trial data from CRFs, operational activity and other data provided by the site, at the location of the site. The trial team are responsible for compiling the list of sites and participants that are to be monitored.

The level of monitoring required should be detailed in the monitoring plan, which will depend on the outcome of the trial’s risk assessment (RA). The frequency and duration of the site monitoring visits will also depend on the level of risk and complexity of the trial, the rate of recruitment at a site and the duration of the trial.

At the site monitoring visit, the DM will then carry out source data verification (SDV) checks of the identified participants files. This involves checking the data received from the site with the data collected at the site and noting any findings in the monitoring report. The DM should also address any data queries with the site personnel at the visit.

Depending on the trial, this process might involve;

- Comparing the CRFs received at the unit with the CRFs at the site.
- Checking the database or a database print out against the patient notes.
- Checking any reported SAEs and endpoint data against the notes.

If any discrepancies are found at the visit, a data query should be raised with the site added to the monitoring report. If possible, the query should be resolved by the site at the visit, however, if not possible, the DM should follow up the data queries with the site following the visit until resolution and update the monitoring report with the actions undertaken and outcome of the query.

E) QUALITY CONTROL OF DATA

The research outcomes of a trial are only as good as the data upon which the conclusions are formed. When research findings are used to develop new treatment recommendations, changes to best practice and health policies they inevitably will have an impact on patients' lives and therefore must be based on accurate, robust and reproducible data. To that end, all trials must have procedures in place at each stage of data handling to ensure that the data is reliable and has been generated, managed, analysed and reported according to the approved trial protocol, SOP's and in line with regulatory frameworks. This is quality control (QC). It is an integral part of GCP guidelines and is defined as 'the operational techniques and activities undertaken within the quality assurance system to verify that the requirements for quality of the trial-related activities have been fulfilled.'

The exact nature and frequency of the QC checks needed in each trial will be study specific and dependent on a variety of factors such as the complexity of the study (e.g. CTIMP vs non-CTIMP, observational study etc.) and the degree of risk level associated with it (low, medium or high risk studies).

These should be agreed within the trial team during the trial set-up period and clearly documented in the risk assessment document and data management plan (DMP) as they will drive the specific QC procedures to be undertaken.

Many QC activities are embedded within clinical trial unit SOP's so adhering to these will show compliance with QC procedures. All QC checks must be documented and the documented evidence of QC retained within the TMF. Examples of data QC checks may include processes to:

- Check data entry accuracy, including Source Data Verification (SDV)
- Identify and resolve incorrect or missing data
- Ensure consistency across documentation
- Review Safety Data
- Ensure data collection is consistent with the protocol

The specifics of QC checks should be reviewed periodically to ensure they remain appropriate throughout the progress of the trial. They can be amended as necessary, in light of developments such as a significant change in the number of data queries, substantial changes to the trial protocol, number of participants or sites and if there are any concerns regarding the conduct of the trial.

The method of data collection (e.g. paper CRF's (pCRF's) or electronic data capture (EDC)) will also dictate some of the QC procedures that will be required.

QC for data captured by EDC methods will form part of the SDV process of on-site monitoring as described above. The percentage of data requiring verification should be agreed during the trial set up. Validations will be built in as part of the database development and testing, to limit the entry of incorrect or implausible data values and maximise the completeness and consistency of manually-entered trial data. Any data that violates a validation rule will trigger an alert to the site user to check the value before progressing and either correct it or provide a reason for the out of range/unexpected data.

For trials using pCRF's, an agreed percentage of forms will need to be checked for accuracy against the data entered onto the trial database. This should be done by someone other than who entered the data originally. An acceptable error rate (for example no higher than 1%), the point at which the data QC takes place (e.g. after a certain number of participants have been enrolled or after a set time period) and what happens if an error is discovered must be documented in the DMP.

The error rate can be calculated as follows:

$$\frac{\text{Number of fields with errors}}{\text{Number of fields checked}} \times 100$$

If the error rate is below that which has been decided is acceptable, corrections should be made with full documentation of correspondence retained. If the error rate is above that which is deemed acceptable, this should be escalated to the study team to discuss further action.

The process of QC for SAE data will depend on the level of risk of the trial and at a minimum should occur once during the trial and once at the end. Again, the proportion of SAE's to be checked should be agreed and documented during set up.

F) AUDIT TRAIL CHECKING

The data audit trail within a clinical trial is a secure digital record which captures the who, what, when, and why of electronic data creation, amendment and deletion. It is an activity log containing metadata about each step of the life-cycle of the data without obscuring or overwriting the original record and is vital for compliance with regulatory frameworks.

An audit trail should include the following information to allow any activity to be reconstructed:

- The identity of the person performing the action
- Details of the action whilst maintaining a record of the original entry
- The reason for the action
- The date and time the action was performed

All trial databases will have in-built audit facilities to satisfy regulatory requirements, which should be fully tested and validated during the database set up to ensure the necessary information is collected accurately.

During the trial, the audit trail must be checked regularly (the frequency should be documented in the data management plan) in order to safeguard data integrity. This may also help to identify issues with data entry/accuracy that can be resolved in a timely manner and highlight the need for further training. Changes to data must be justified and robust reasons for changes to data are recorded in the audit trail. Any excessive user or site changes should be queried.

If unauthorised or incorrect data changes are identified, the site should be contacted to re-enter the correct data or confirm its accuracy. All email correspondence and audit trail logs should be filed within the TMF.

The audit log should also be reviewed by a senior data manager to ensure no unauthorised changes were made by the trial DM. If this is the case the reason for any changes by the DM should be investigated, the accuracy of the data confirmed with sites and a SOP deviation logged.

G) PROCESSING WITHDRAWALS

A participant can leave a research study at any time. When withdrawing from the study, the participant should let the research team know that he/she/they wishes to withdraw.

The Withdrawal form for a study should ensure that it matches the levels of withdrawal in the protocol. Examples of those could be:

- Discontinuation of trial treatment
- Withdrawal from further trial visits
- Withdrawal from further data submission
- Withdrawal from further sample collection (if applicable)
- Withdrawal from further QoL collection (if applicable)
- Withdrawal from any previous data to be used
- Withdrawal from any previous samples to be used

The Data Manager is responsible for reviewing the withdrawal CRF upon receipt. The database in the case of EDC). Participants can withdraw from multiple aspects of the study and therefore, care needs to be taken when reviewing withdrawal forms to ensure any further actions are implemented e.g. informing labs if samples should be deleted or ensuring further questionnaires should not be sent.

6) KEY PRINCIPLES AND CONSIDERATIONS FOR A DATA MANAGER IN A CLINICAL TRIAL THAT HAS CLOSED TO RECRUITMENT

A) FINALISING DATA FOR ANALYSIS

Before locking data and getting it ready for analysis we need to make sure that we covered all the following points.

- Ensuring the accuracy and completeness for all data.
- Ensuring that all data been entered without errors.
- Ensuring all missing data been resolved/reasonable reason provided.
- Locking the data to prevent any changes.
- Preparing the data for export on the right format for analysis.
- Documenting all the finalising processes that been performed to data to get it ready for analysis.
- Having back up stored data before sending it to analysis.

B) DATABASE LOCK

Database lock) is a critical step in clinical trial data management which occurs after trial data has been collected, verified, and cleaned. Database lock is the process of approving and finalizing the completed data set, and “locking it” to further changes.

Database lock can be initiated once the trial protocol has been completed and all clinical data has been collected and entered into the database. All data queries should be resolved and the data should be in a verified and validated state. There should be evidence of data reconciliation between finalised CRFs and other source documents such as patient medical records, and clinical monitors should certify that they have completed required safety reviews for each subject and reviewed any discrepancies in individual patients’ data.

When the clinical database is locked, no further changes can be made to the data without authorization from an authorised signatory (e.g. a director), generally only the lead clinical data manager will have edit rights and any changes will require unlocking.

Database lock in clinical trials is a crucial process that helps researchers ensure data accuracy and consistency, and which prevents the study data from unwanted or unauthorized changes after data has been verified and all corrections have been made. Database locking usually proceeds via two steps - soft lock and hard lock - and the hard locked database, considered “final,” is used in the analysis to generate the trial’s final results. Clinical trial databases can be unlocked under specific circumstances, namely when a critical error is identified which requires correction within the database. Both database lock and unlocking procedures should be clearly defined and outlined in SOPs in order to guarantee regulatory compliance.

C) RETURNING DATA TO SITES

When using Electronic Data Capture in a trial or study, it is important to remember that the data that is collected belongs to the investigator at site and not to the sponsor or clinical trials unit. In Good Clinical Practice (section 8.3.14) there is a requirement that the data remains under the control of the investigator at all times and for supplying a copy of the clinical trial data and the audit trail to investigators at the end of a trial where Electronic Data capture is employed in the trial. (If data is collected on paper case report forms this will not apply as a site should ensure that a copy of the case report form is contained in their site file).

The following should be considered for returning data to sites

- During database set up consider how you are going to extract data on a site-by-site basis to allow it's return
- Also, during the set-up phase consider how you will return the audit trail on a site-by-site basis.
- A dataset should not be returned to site until the trial statistician approves. If the database has been locked a site should retain read only access to the database until the datasets are ready to be returned.
- A process should be in place to check that the datasets contain the correct participant IDs to ensure the correct data is being sent to sites.
- Sites should be contacted to ask the format in which the data should be returned to them to allow them to view it. A recommended format is csv.
- Sites should be sent the data dictionary / data matrix alongside the datasets, so they are able to interpret the data.
- Datasets should be sent to sites password protected and sent via a secure file transfer portal.
- Sites should be contacted to ensure they have received the datasets and are able to open them.

7. RECCOMENDED DATA MANAGEMENT TRAINING

ACDM Online Training

The Association of Clinical Data Management (ACDM) run online training courses. At the time of writing these are priced at £50 each. Each session includes interactive voice and media presentation self-assessments, an examination and a completion certificate. The current topics that are offered are:

- Fundamentals of Clinical Data Management
- ECG & Holter Data
- Management of Non-CRF Data
- RECIST for Data Managers
- Building data management success in Sponsor CRO relationships
- Preparing for Regulatory Inspections
- Data Integrity
- Risk Based Monitoring
- Data Validation and Effective Query writing
- Risk based monitoring
- Understanding laboratory data

More details on these courses can be found on the ACDM website <https://acdmglobal.org/acdm-online-training/>

ACDM Hot Topics

The ACDM also offer 'Hot Topic sessions These are held online as 'discussions' focussing on a topic in Data Management. They are free for ACDM members (small fee for Non-Members).

As they are 'discussions' they are different to webinars and no presentation slides are prepared.

8. CAREERS AND PROGRESSION IN DATA MANAGEMENT

Data Management teams generally have different roles in them. Other than a Data Manager other roles could include:

- Senior Data Manager
- Head of Data Management
- Data Specialist
- Data Analysts.

Once you have established yourself in the Data Management role you should look at job descriptions for senior roles in your institution and across other institutions to establish the criteria you will need to meet to be successful in progressing in your role.

University Data Management roles are all advertised on the institutions website alongside jobs.ac.uk

Other Data Management roles maybe found on the Association of Clinical Data Management website.

9. PUBLISHING DATA MANAGEMENT OUTPUTS

Often Data Managers will have another element to their role as a researcher as well. If you have this as part of your role or not it is important that any new Data Management methodology is published and presented at conferences. Journals such as Trials are always looking to present methodological outputs and conferences such as the International Clinical Trials Methodology Conference (ICTMC) is one of the best places to present this work.

Data Managers might look to develop or implement a SWAT. A SWAT is a self-contained research study that has been embedded within a host trial with the aim of evaluating or exploring alternative ways of delivering or organising a particular trial process.

It seeks to resolve important uncertainties about the processes used in trials. It can be evaluated in a single trial but is well-suited for running across more than one host trial, either at the same time or sequentially. It will provide data to inform the design and conduct of future trials but might also provide data to inform decisions about the ongoing host trial. All published SWAT protocols are published on the Northern Ireland repository.

<https://www.qub.ac.uk/sites/TheNorthernIrelandNetworkforTrialsMethodologyResearch/SWATSWA/Information/Repositories/SWATStore/>

SWATs results should be made public, so that the evidence base available for future decisions can increase. The findings can then be picked up by systematic reviewers and others who synthesise research evidence.

Examples of Data type SWATs are:

- How does offering a choice of data collection mode affect recruitment and data collection in a feasibility study of a cancer symptom awareness intervention (TIC-TOC Study)?
<https://www.qub.ac.uk/sites/TheNorthernIrelandNetworkforTrialsMethodologyResearch/FileStore/Fileupload,1608995,en.pdf>
- Impact of data collection frequency on participant retention in the HEAL-COVID platform clinical trial
<https://www.qub.ac.uk/sites/TheNorthernIrelandNetworkforTrialsMethodologyResearch/FileStore/Fileupload,1794817,en.pdf>
- Electronic versus paper based Patient Reported oUtcomes ColleCtion (SPRUICE)
<https://www.qub.ac.uk/sites/TheNorthernIrelandNetworkforTrialsMethodologyResearch/FileStore/Fileupload,1425888,en.pdf>
- Modes of data collection for subjective outcomes at follow-up: comparing a choice and a failure-based approach
<https://www.qub.ac.uk/sites/TheNorthernIrelandNetworkforTrialsMethodologyResearch/FileStore/Fileupload,1072375,en.pdf>

The above are a few examples of SWATs in the repository, it is worth reviewing the repository to see if you can implement any into your trials or studies. If you have an idea for a SWAT even if you don't think you are able to implement into a trial or study that you are working on, it will be still important that this is written up so that other researchers can implement it and add to the methodological evidence. Have a look at how a SWAT protocol should be laid out in the repository.

As well as SWATs other examples of work that can be published and presented at conferences, such as work on implementing two-way text messages into trials and participant led database design.

Being able to publish data management methodology allows for the evidence base to be increased but also allows for the work a data manager does to be highlighted to other researchers.

APPENDIX 1 – Data Management through the lifecycle of a trial (Flow chart)